

Kinetics of the peroxomonosulfate oxidation of sulfur(-II) compounds : thioacetamide, dithiooxamide and thiourea[†]

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Manuscript received 5 October 2009, accepted 9 October 2009

Abstract : Kinetics of relatively faster oxidation of thioacetamide (TA), dithiooxamide (DTO) and thiourea (TU) by peroxomonosulfate (PMS) has been studied spectrophotometrically under pseudo order condition by keeping oxidant in excess. Under these conditions, the sulfur(-II) compounds are oxidized to corresponding S-dioxides. The kinetics rate law for the oxidation of TA and TU both is eq. (A) and for the oxidation of DTO is eq. (B).

$$-\frac{d[S(-II)]}{dt} = \frac{kK [PMS] [S(-II)]}{1+K [H^+]} \quad (A)$$

$$-\frac{d[DTO]}{dt} = k [DMS] [DTO] \quad (B)$$

The values of rate constant, *k*, at 30 °C were 3.4 (DTO), 44 (TA) and 3.4 L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ (TU) and those of protonation constants, *K*, were 3.2 (TU) and 19 (TA). A comparative rate analysis showed oxidation by PMS to be much faster than with H₂O₂.

Keywords : Peroxomonosulfate, thiourea, thioacetamide, dithiooxamide, oxidation, kinetics.

Introduction

Peroxomonosulfate (PMS), which is a strong oxidant, finds several usage in industrial and environmental control processes, e.g. in washing and bleaching of textiles, initiation of polymerization, cyanide removal, metal reclamation, hydrometallurgy, purification of waste water and the control of malodorous reduced sulfur compounds. Aside from industrial applications, PMS is an important natural oxidant in atmospheric aqueous systems¹⁻⁴. One of the major sources of PMS in atmosphere aqueous system is the oxidation of dissolved SO₂, i.e. S^{IV} by hydroxyl radicals, which results in the formation of SO₃⁻ radical. The latter reacts rapidly with O₂ to form peroxomonosulfate radical ion³. The reaction of latter with S^{IV} and other reducing agents leads to the formation of HSO₅⁻.

Likewise, the autoxidation of sulfur(IV) catalyzed by trace metal ions such as, Fe^{III}/Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} etc. acts as an important source of PMS⁵.

The oxidation of sulfur(IV) by PMS is known to be quite fast⁴, and understanding the mechanism of the oxidation of sulfur compounds by PMS is relevant to atmospheric chemistry. Recently in the sulfur(IV)-O₂-Ni^{II}, the formation of PMS or a PMS-like species has been shown^{6,7}. Looking to the importance of oxidation of sulfur compounds by PMS, we decided to study the oxidation of thioacetamide (TA) and dithiooxamide or rubeanic acid (DTO) in detail by PMS and compare the results with the oxidation of H₂S⁸, dimethyl sulfide⁹, diethyl sulfide⁹ and sulfoxides¹⁰ etc. Results of a preliminary study on thiourea (TU) are also included.

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

A literature survey revealed that the oxidation of thioacetamide (TA), which is used as a source of sulfur in rubber industry, has not been the subject of much study. Kinetics of its oxidation with peroxodisulfate-catalyzed by silver(I)¹¹, octacyanomolybdate(V)¹², hexacyanoferrate(III)¹³ and ferrate(VI)¹⁴ has been reported.

Dithiooxamide or rubeanic acid is a well known analytical reagent for a large number of transition metal ions such as copper, nickel, cobalt, tungsten, ruthenium, technetium etc. Its oxidation with periodate¹⁵ and hydrogen peroxide¹⁵ has been mentioned. H₂O₂ oxidation reaction is catalyzed by W^{IV}¹⁶ and the oxidation product is dithio-S,S'-dioxide oxamide¹⁷. This reaction has been used as the kinetics method for the determination of the trace amount of W^{IV} in solution. Kinetics of its oxidation by chloramine-T has also been reported^{18(a)}.

The oxidation of thiourea by chloramine-T^{18(b)}, H₂O₂¹⁹, bromate/bromine²⁰, iodate²¹, permanganate²², 12-tungstocobaltate(III)²³ and several metal ions and their complexes²³ has been studied.

Experimental

Peroxomonosulfate was obtained from Aldrich in the form of a triple salt, 2KHSO₅.KHSO₄.K₂SO₄ (OXONE). Iodometric assay indicated the peroxomonosulfate (PMS) content to be ~85%. Thioacetamide (Sisco-chem), dithiooxamide (Sereal), perchloric acid (Reidel) and all other chemicals of reagent grade were used. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The kinetics was followed spectrophotometrically on Hitach-U-2000 spectrophotometer, which directly recorded the absorbance at pre-

determined time intervals, at the desired wavelength. The temperature of the cell was maintained by circulating the thermostated water. The applicability of the Beer's law was checked in each case.

The kinetics, which was studied under pseudo-order conditions - peroxomonosulfate (PMS) being at least ten times in excess over reductant, followed first order course in all cases. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were calculated using the eq. (5).

$$k_{obs} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{(A_0 - A_{\infty})}{(A_t - A_{\infty})} \quad (5)$$

where A_0 , A_t and A_{∞} , are absorbance values initially, at time t and at the end of the reaction. The replicate measurements were generally reproducible within $\pm 5\%$. All calculations were performed on MS-excel.

Results

Stoichiometry and UV-Visible spectra :

The oxidation reactions of sulfur(-II) compounds are in general quite complex. Oxidation of these compounds with peroxo compounds yields products in which sulfur is present in different oxidation states from -I in disulfides to +IV in sulfate. The stoichiometry of both TA and DTO was determined by performing spectrophotometric titration. For this purpose reaction mixtures with varying [PMS] and fixed [TA] or [DTO] were prepared and the absorbencies were recorded after 12 h to allow sufficient time for completion of the reaction.

In case of TA, the results shown in Fig. 1 indicate three points of inflexion at [PMS]/[TA] ratios of ~0.5,

Fig. 1. The variation of absorbance with [PMS] at [TA] = 2.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹, [HClO₄] = 0.1 mol L⁻¹, λ = 206.5 nm and at t = 30 °C.

~1.5, ~2.1 indicating the formation of intermediate products and that when [PMS]/[TA] is high, as in the present kinetics study, the main product is thioacetamide-S-dioxide corresponding to stoichiometric eq. (6).

The UV-Visible spectra of TA and PMS and reaction mixtures are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. λ_{max} values of 206.5 and 259 nm in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ solu-

Fig. 2. The spectra of PMS-TA system at [HClO₄] = 0.1 mol L⁻¹ and at 30 °C : (a) [thioacetamide] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹; (b) [peroxomonosulfate] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; (c) [PMS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ and [TA] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ (after completion of the reaction).

Fig. 3. The spectra of PMS-TA reaction mixtures at different [PMS] at [TA] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹, [HClO₄] = 0.1 mol L⁻¹ and at 30 °C. [PMS] = (a) 1.0 × 10⁻⁴; (b) 2.5 × 10⁻⁴; (c) 3.5 × 10⁻⁴; (d) 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹.

tion for TA agree with reported values of 210 and 261 nm in aqueous solution²⁴. The spectra of reaction mixtures at different [PMS]/[TA] ratios show the appearance of a new peak, which was absent in TA. This provides the evidence for the formation of intermediate product, as indicated by spectrophotometric titration. When the [PMS]/[TA] is high the absorbance at both 206.5 and 229 nm wavelengths decreases continuously (Fig. 3), showing the conversion of intermediate(s) into the final product. It must be pointed out that the obtaining spectral evidence for an intermediate depends upon its relative concentration, its rate of oxidation, its molar extinction coefficient and finally on the [PMS]/[TA] ratio.

UV-Visible spectra of DTO shown in Fig. 4 indicate a λ_{max} value of 300 nm in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ solution. Following the similar procedure, as in the case of TA, the results of spectrophotometric titration (Fig. 5) and spectra of reaction mixtures obtained at different [PMS]/[DTO] ratio are given in Figs. 6 and 7. The two points of inflexions in Fig. 5 at [PMS]/[DTO] ratios of ~2.0 and

Fig. 4. The spectra of PMS-DTO system at [HClO₄] = 0.01 mol L⁻¹ and at *t* = 30 °C. (a) [DTO] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹; (b) [PMS] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; (c) [DTO] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹ and [PMS] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ (after completion of the reaction).

Fig. 5. The variation of absorbance with [PMS] at [DTO] = 4.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹, [HClO₄] = 0.01 mol L⁻¹, λ = 232 nm and at *t* = 30 °C.

Fig. 6. The spectra of PMS-DTO reaction mixtures at different [PMS] and [DTO] = 4.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹; [H⁺] = 0.01 mol L⁻¹ and at $t = 30$ °C. [PMS] = (a) 1.0×10^{-4} ; (b) 2.0×10^{-4} ; (c) 3.0×10^{-4} ; (d) 4.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹.

Fig. 7. The spectra of PMS-DTO reaction mixtures at different [PMS] and [DTO] = 4.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹; [HClO₄] = 0.01 mol L⁻¹ and at $t = 30$ °C. [PMS] = (a) 1.2×10^{-3} ; (b) 1.4×10^{-3} ; (c) 1.6×10^{-3} ; (d) 1.8×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹.

~4.0 indicate the formation of an intermediate product and that when [PMS]/[DTO] ratio is high main reaction product corresponds to 1 : 4 stoichiometry as in eq. (7).

The spectra of reaction mixtures (Fig. 6) at different [PMS]/[DTO] ratios shows the DTO peak at 300 nm to disappear between [PMS]/[DTO] \approx 0.25–1.0 and new peaks to appear at 248 and 335 nm. The Fig. 6 also shows two isobestic points indicating the conversion of DTO into another oxidized product. When [PMS]/[DTO] > 1, the absorbance of the reaction mixture decreases continuously without the formation of any new peak (Fig. 7). Ultimately, when the reaction is over, the spectra shown in Fig. 7 are obtained.

Rate laws :

The kinetics, which in each case was studied under pseudo-first order conditions with [PMS] being in excess, was found to be first order in each of [PMS] and reductant, [S(-II)]. The nature of reaction profiles and some pseudo-first order plots for TA and DTO are shown in Figs. 8–9 and 10–11, respectively.

Fig. 8. Change in absorbance with time at $\lambda = 335$ nm. [PMS] = 3.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹, [DTO] = 3.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹, [HClO₄] = 0.01 mol L⁻¹ and at $t = 30$ °C.

Fig. 9. Change in absorbance with time at [TA] = 5.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹, [PMS] = 3.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹, [HClO₄] = 0.05 mol L⁻¹, $\lambda = 241$ nm and at $t = 30$ °C.

Fig. 10. The pseudo-first order plots of DTO-PMS reaction at $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.01 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{PMS}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$, $[\text{DTO}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (5); 2.0×10^{-4} (4); 3.0×10^{-4} (3); 4.0×10^{-4} (2); $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ (1).

Fig. 11. The pseudo-first order plots of TA-PMS reaction at $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{PMS}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $t = 30^\circ\text{C}$, $[\text{TA}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (5); 2.0×10^{-4} (4); 3.0×10^{-4} (3); 4.0×10^{-4} (2); $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ (1).

DTO oxidation : The kinetics was studied at $[\text{PMS}]/[\text{DTO}] = 10\text{--}50$ by following the decrease in the absorbance of DTO at 335 nm at which neither PMS nor product had any appreciable absorbance. The results are in agreement with the rate law (8).

$$-\frac{d[\text{DTO}]}{dt} = k [\text{DMS}] [\text{DTO}] \quad (8)$$

where $k_{\text{obs}} = k [\text{PMS}]$. The values of k determined at different $[\text{PMS}]$ and $[\text{DTO}]$ are in good agreement with each other as given in Table 1. The DTO oxidation was found to be practically independent of $[\text{H}^+]$, when $[\text{HClO}_4]$

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , for HSO_5^- -dithioamide (DTO) reaction

$10^3 [\text{PMS}]$ (mol L^{-1})	$10^4 [\text{DTO}]$ (mol L^{-1})	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ (mol L^{-1})	t ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$10^2 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})	k ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
5	1	0.01	25	1.34	2.7
5	2	0.01	25	1.27	2.5
5	3	0.01	25	1.15	2.3
5	4	0.01	25	1.25	2.5
5	5	0.01	25	1.07	2.2
6	1	0.01	25	1.31	2.2
6	2	0.01	25	1.3	2.2
6	3	0.01	25	1.21	2.0
6	4	0.01	25	1.25	2.1
4	2	0.01	25	1.09	2.7
6	2	0.01	25	1.49	2.5
8	2	0.01	25	1.95	2.4
10	2	0.01	25	2.65	2.6
13	2	0.01	25	3.65	2.8
18	2	0.01	25	4.45	2.5
4	4	0.01	25	1.1	2.7
6	4	0.01	25	1.41	2.4
8	4	0.01	25	1.9	2.4
10	4	0.01	25	2.6	2.6
13	4	0.01	25	2.7	2.1
18	4	0.01	25	4.4	2.4
4	4	0.01	25	1.09	2.7
4	4	0.05	25	1.09	2.7
4	4	0.075	25	1.1	2.7
4	4	0.10	25	1.12	2.8
4	4	0.25	25	0.96	2.4
4	4	0.50	25	0.92	2.3
4	2	0.01	25	1.1	2.7
4	2	0.50	25	0.97	2.4
3	3	0.01	25	0.54	1.8
3	3	0.01	29	1.03	3.4
3	3	0.01	34	2.3	7.7

was varied in the range 0.01–0.5 mol L⁻¹. The ionic strength was also without any effect. From the values of *k* at different temperature, the overall empirical energy of activation was found to be 123 kJ mol⁻¹.

Thioacetamide oxidation : The kinetics was studied at 241 nm at which TA absorbed strongly and PMS and final product did not have any significant absorbance. The results of variation in [PMS] {(0.2–1.0) × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹} and [TA] {(1–5) × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹} at fixed [H⁺] were defined by the rate laws (9–10).

$$-\frac{d[S(-II)]}{dt} = k_2 [S(-II)] [PMS] \quad (9)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_2 [PMS] \quad (10)$$

The values of *k*_{obs} and *k*₂ are collected in Table 2. The plot of *k*_{obs} versus [PMS] was found to be linear passing through origin.

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}, for HSO₅⁻-thioacetamide (TA) reaction

10 ⁴ [TA] (mol L ⁻¹)	10 ³ [PMS] (mol L ⁻¹)	[HClO ₄] (mol L ⁻¹)	<i>t</i> (°C)	10 ² <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> ₂ (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
1	3	0.10	30	6.90	23
2	3	0.10	30	6.45	21
3	3	0.10	30	6.22	21
4	3	0.10	30	5.87	20
5	3	0.10	30	5.53	18
1	5	0.10	30	12.4	25
2	5	0.10	30	11.7	23
3	5	0.10	30	10.4	21
4	5	0.10	30	9.80	20
5	5	0.10	30	9.20	18
1	7.5	0.85	30	2.44	3.3
2	7.5	0.85	30	2.15	2.9
3	7.5	0.85	30	2.21	2.9
4	7.5	0.85	30	2.19	2.9
5	7.5	0.85	30	2.31	3.1
2	2	0.85	30	0.63	3.1
2	3	0.85	30	0.92	3.1
2	4	0.85	30	1.15	2.9
2	5	0.85	30	1.33	2.7
2	6	0.85	30	1.72	2.9
2	7	0.85	30	2.14	3.1
2	8	0.85	30	2.20	2.7
2	8.5	0.85	30	2.65	3.1
2	10	0.85	30	2.76	2.8
3	2	0.85	30	0.59	3.0
3	3	0.85	30	0.90	3.0

Table-2 (contd.)

3	4	0.85	30	1.10	2.8
3	5	0.85	30	1.30	2.6
3	6	0.85	30	1.70	2.8
3	7	0.85	30	2.12	3.0
3	8	0.85	30	2.56	3.0
3	10	0.85	30	2.79	2.8
5	2	0.85	30	0.48	2.4
5	3	0.85	30	0.96	3.1
5	4	0.85	30	1.02	2.6
5	5	0.85	30	1.26	2.5
5	6	0.85	30	1.68	2.8
5	7	0.85	30	2.15	3.1
5	8.5	0.85	30	2.46	2.9
5	10	0.85	30	2.81	2.0
5	3	0.05	30	6.91	23.0
5	3	0.10	30	5.50	18.0
5	3	0.25	30	2.30	7.7
5	3	0.50	30	1.20	4.0
5	3	0.80	30	0.87	2.9
5	3	0.05	34.5	8.59	29.0
5	3	0.10	34.5	6.44	22.0
5	3	0.25	34.5	3.22	11.0
5	3	0.50	34.5	1.64	5.5
5	3	0.80	34.5	1.15	3.8
2	5	0.85	30	1.32	2.6
2	5	0.85	35	1.90	3.8
2	5	0.85	38	2.20	4.4

Dependence of the reaction rate on [H⁺] was investigated by varying the concentration of perchloric acid in the range (0.1–0.8) mol L⁻¹. Results show the rate to decrease with increase in [H⁺]. An analysis of the dependence of *k*_{obs} on [H⁺] showed it to fit the rate law (11).

$$k_{obs} = \frac{kK [PMS]}{1 + K [H^+]} \quad (11)$$

where *k*₂ = *kK*/(1 + *K*[H⁺]), *k* is the rate constant and *K* is the protonation constant of thioacetamide. The latter on rearranging becomes,

$$\frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{K [H^+]}{k} \quad (12)$$

On plotting 1/*k*₂ against [H⁺], a straight line with a non-zero intercept was obtained (Fig. 12). From the values of slope and intercept of this plot, the values of *k* and *K* were obtained (Table 3).

Table 3. Rate parameters for thioacetamide (TA), thiourea (TU) and dithiooxamide (DTO)

Rate parameters	TA	TU	DTO
k (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	44 (30 °C)	2.7 (26.5 °C)	1.8 (25 °C)
	54 (34.5 °C)	4.3 (30 °C)	3.4 (29 °C)
	-	5.0 (34 °C)	7.7 (34 °C)
K	19 (30 °C)	2.4 (26.5 °C)	-
	17 (34.5 °C)	3.2 (30 °C)	-
	-	2.8 (34 °C)	-

The ionic strength, which was examined by varying lithium perchlorate in the range (0.1–1.0) mol L⁻¹, did not influence the rate of reaction. The values of k_2 at different temperatures are given in Table 2. From the plot of $\log k_2$ vs T^{-1} , the value of overall energy of activation was determined to be 22 kJ mol⁻¹.

Thiourea oxidation : For the sake of comparison, a preliminary kinetics of thiourea-PMS reaction was also undertaken. The spectrophotometric titration data indicated two points of inflexions at [PMS]/[TU] ratios of ~1 and ~2. Thus, when PMS is in excess, TU is oxidized to corresponding S-dioxide. The kinetics was found to obey the rate laws (9–11). The values of k and K are given in Table 3.

Discussion

General peroxide oxidation mechanism :

The oxidation reactions of peroxy compounds, e.g. PMS, H₂O₂ etc. usually follow a second order kinetics, being first order in each of peroxide and the reducing substrate. Consequently, the proposed mechanisms involve a bimolecular rate determining step in which both peroxide and substrate participate. For 2-equivalent nucleophilic reductants, Hoffmann and Edwards¹⁹ and Ball and Edwards²⁵ have proposed the following general mechanism, which involves the attack of substrate (nucleophile, Nu) on peroxide (–O–O–) bond, as shown in eq. (13).

The species in parenthesis may represent a transition state or an intermediate, the subsequent heterolytic fission of

–O–O– bond leads to the formation of the products via transfer of an oxygen atom from the peroxide bond to the reducing agent. Experimental evidence for this has been provided by use of labeled HSO₃⁻ in the oxidation²⁷ of Cr(NH₃)₅N₃²⁺ in to Cr(NH₃)₅NO₂⁺ and that of²⁸ [(NH₃)₅CoS₂O₃]⁺ in to [(NH₃)₅CoS₂O₅]⁺.

Indeed, in the oxidation of sulfur compounds, such as H₂S⁸, HS⁻⁸, diethyl sulfide⁹, dimethyl sulfide⁹, dimethyl sulfoxide¹⁰ by both hydrogen peroxide and PMS oxygen is added to sulfur atom, in general. These reactions can yield a variety of differently oxidized products. In this connection, the study of the oxidation of thiourea by H₂O₂ by Gao *et al.*²⁹ is quite interesting and provides an insight and clue to the possible mechanisms and relative rates of consecutive peroxide oxidation steps in the oxidation of sulfur compounds with various peroxide oxidants. Gao *et al.*²⁹ used reversed-phase ion-pair high performance liquid chromatography to monitor the concentrations of variety of sulfur containing species with differing oxidation states and to quantitatively characterize the oxidation kinetics of thiourea–H₂O₂ reaction. The mechanism comprising eight steps with corresponding rate constants is given below.

The values of rate constants of individual oxidation steps indicate the rate of oxidation of organic sulfur species to decrease with increase in sulfur oxidation number. For example, the order of reactivity with H_2O_2 is : $(NH_2)_2CS > NH_2(NH)CSSC(NH)NH_2 > (NH_2)_2CSO > (NH_2)_2CSO_2 > (NH_2)_2CSO_3$. It is also revealed that under the condition $[H_2O_2] > [(NH_2)_2CS]$, the reaction would proceed to rate determining step $(NH_2)_2CSO_2$ only the further oxidation would be very slow. The rate determining step would be the oxidation of $(NH_2)_2CSO$.

Mechanism of oxidation of thioacetamide/dithioamide/thiourea :

Before discussing the mechanism of the oxidation of chosen sulfur(-II) compounds, it is necessary to discuss their speciation in aqueous acidic solutions. Since the first dissociation constant²⁵ of H_2SO_5 is quite high ($pK_1 < 0$) and the second dissociation constant is very low ($pK_2 = 9.4$), in the $[H^+]$ range (0.05–0.85 mol L⁻¹), the PMS would largely exist as HSO_5^- and hence the observed $[H^+]$ -dependence in case of TA and TU can not be adduced to PMS. The protonation of TA is well known and the value of pK_a for the acid dissociation of its conjugate acid, $CH_3(NH_3^+)CS$ (TAH^+), is reported to be 1.19²⁴. This indicates that in the range of acidity used in this study both unprotonated and monoprotonated thioacetamide species would be present. The protonation of thiourea is well known ($TU + H^+ \rightleftharpoons TUH^+$). DTO is a very strong base and pK_a value²⁶ of 10.89 (25 °C) of the acid dissociation of monoprotonated dithiooxamide indicates it to exist largely in monoprotonated form ($DTOH^+$) in the range of $[H^+]$ used in this study. So in constructing reaction mechanism, species, HSO_5^- , TA, TAH^+ , TU, TOH^+ and $DTOH^+$ only have been taken into account and HSO_5^- , TA, TU and $DTOH^+$ have been assumed reactive.

The nature of hydrogen ion dependence and the rate law (11) suggest that only unprotonated TA takes part in oxidation reaction, TAH^+ being unreactive. The following mechanism may be proposed for the oxidation of TA by PMS.

The mechanism of oxidation of TA is similar to those proposed in case of the oxidation of dimethyl sulfide, diethyl sulfide, DMSO and other substrates. In case of thiourea- H_2O_2 reaction (eqs. (14–21)), the oxidation of TU in to $H_2NCSONH_2$ is seen to be much faster than the oxidation of $H_2NCSONH_2$ in to $NH_2CSO_2NH_2$. Likewise, in the oxidation of TA also the steps (23–24) have been assumed to be fast and the step (25) to be the rate-determining. Had the rate of the steps (23–24) been different than that of step (25), the pseudo-first order plots (Figs. 10 and 11) should have been biphasic, that is, showing two straight lines with different slopes meeting at a point³⁰. Since all the points fall on the same straight line in Figs. 10 and 11, it is reasonable to assume the steps (23–24) to be fast. Since the kinetics of TU oxidation is similar to TA oxidation, a similar mechanism can be written for TU also.

In the oxidation of DTO, the spectrophotometric titration data indicate the formation of more than one intermediate. When $[PMS]/[DTO]$ ratio is high, as in the experimental conditions of this study, the oxidation proceeds to the final product, i.e. dithio-S,S'-dioxide oxamide. Obviously, the kinetics, that we have followed, relates to the oxidation of intermediate product, $H_2NCSO_2-CSONH_2$ into the final product, $H_2NCSO_2-CSO_2NH_2$. On the basis of the results of spectrophotometric titration, spectra of reaction mixtures and the kinetics rate law (8), the following simple mechanism, which may contain some other steps – which kinetics is unable to identify – may be proposed.

Since the oxidation of >CS to >CSO group appears²⁹ to be faster than the oxidation of >CSO to >CSO₂, the steps (27–29) are assumed to be fast. The direct oxidation of (H₂NCSO)₂ to (H₂NCSO₂)₂ in a single step will require two molecules of HSO₅⁻. Had this been the case, the dependence of rate on [PMS] would have been second order. As this is not the case, the reaction (30), which is slow and rate-determining, has been proposed.

It is of interest to compare the values of protonation constants of TU (TU + H⁺ ⇌ TUH⁺) and TA (eq. (22)) with those reported in the literature. The kinetically

determined value of *K* for TA is 18, which is in good agreement with the value of 24 determined by Hosoya *et al.*²⁴. The kinetically determined *K* value of 3.55 for TU is in the neighborhood of the recommended *K* value²³ of 15. However, Schiessl *et al.*³¹ have questioned several determined values of p*K*_a for thiourea.

Comparison of PMS and H₂O₂ oxidations :

A comparison of the rates of the oxidation of three sulfur compounds, chosen for this study, by PMS, shows the trend : TA > TU ~ DTO. The higher rate of the oxidation of TA than TU has been noted in the oxidation by octacyanomolybdate(v)¹² also, and has been ascribed to inductive effect of methyl group and same could be true in our case too. The rate constants for the oxidation of some sulfur compounds with PMS are given in Table 4. A perusal of rate data shows that the oxidation of the sulfur compounds by PMS to be, in general, fast. The second order rate constants range from 7.7 × 10⁻² for DMSO to 1.22 × 10⁴ for HS⁻ ion. Finally, it is of interest to compare the rates of PMS oxidation of some sulfur compounds with those of H₂O₂ oxidation (Table 4). The values given in Table 4 indicate the PMS oxidation to be much faster as compared to H₂O₂ oxidation. This is probably due to the fact that SO₄²⁻ group is a better leaving group than OH⁻ in the mechanism¹⁹ (eq. (13)).

Table 4. Second order rate constants, *k*, for the oxidation of some substrates with PMS and H₂O₂

Substrate	<i>k</i> (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	
	PMS	H ₂ O ₂
Thiourea	2.7 (26.5 °C) ^a	7 × 10 ⁻² (25 °C) (Ref. 19)
Thioacetamide	44 (30 °C) ^a	Slow
H ₂ S	1.98 × 10 (Ref. 8) (4.9 °C)	8 × 10 ⁻³ (Ref. 8) (4.9 °C)
HS ⁻	1.22 × 10 ⁴ (Ref. 8) (4.9 °C)	4.8 × 10 ⁻¹ (Ref. 8) (4.9 °C)
Cl ⁻	1.4 × 10 ⁻³ (25 °C) (Ref. 32)	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁷ (25 °C) (Ref. 32)
Br ⁻	4.04 (25 °C) (Ref. 32)	2.3 × 10 ⁻⁵ (25 °C) (Ref. 32)
NO ₂ ⁻	0.31 (25 °C) (Ref. 32)	3 × 10 ⁻⁷ (25 °C) (Ref. 32)
	0.14 (25 °C) (Ref. 33)	
Dithioamide	3.4 (30 °C) ^a	Slow
Dimethyl sulfide	0.13 (25 °C) (Ref. 8)	0.034 (Ref. 8)
Diethyl sulfide	0.29 (25 °C) (Ref. 8)	0.02 (Ref. 34)
Dimethyl sulfoxide	0.08 (25 °C) (Ref. 8)	1.02 × 10 ⁻⁴ (Ref. 35)

^aThis work.

Fig. 12. The plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ at different temperatures, TU : (1) 34 °C; (2) 30 °C and (3) 26.5 °C; TA : (4) 30 °C and (5) 34.5 °C.

Acknowledgement

The work was supported by University Grants Commission, New Delhi.

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